

DETECTING DEFECTS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS BY USING INFRARED THERMOGRAPHY

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1 Introduction

Unlike metal alloys having mainly used as materials for the existing structures, composite can be defined as materials that more than two kinds of materials are artificially created to supplement each other's superior properties while sustaining the macroscopic characteristics of each material. There are such representative composite materials as CFRP (Carbon fiber reinforced plastic), GFRP (Glass fiber reinforced plastic), Aramid and FRM (Fiber reinforced metal) widely used in various different industries, such materials have been more used in various different application fields such as aerospace, automobile, railway, building structures and wind power-generation blade. As a technique for quality tests and stability evaluation, NDT (Nondestructive Testing), likely to support such key technologies, can improve enough to be replaced with the existing infrared thermography nondestructive testing, and it is also a very useful technique applicable to composite material structures since it can detect physical properties and defects without destroying objects, such as composite materials, industrial facilities, plants, structures and weld zones, by using radiation, ultrasonic waves, electromagnetism, heat and light energy, etc. In this thesis, the types of delamination of CFRP and GFRP used to create airplane structures were detected through an infrared thermography device. [1,2]

In this thesis, the source of light was used as the source of energy, and by differing the time of investigating the source of light according to the depth of defect, the possibility of detecting defects was judged according to the depth of defect. this thesis could find out the possibility of infrared thermography nondestructive testing.

2. Experimental Materials and Apparatus

2.1 Experimental Materials

The To detect defects inside the laminate of composite materials by using infrared thermography, this study manufactured and compared laminated defect specimen according to the kinds of defects (delamination), defect size and defect depth in laminate, and the composite materials used for this experiment were as follows: Firstly, as a material widely used for aerospace, Cycom 5276-1 G40-800-24K UD Tape, created by synthesizing Cycom 5276-1 epoxy resin with high-strength T800 one-way carbon fiber, was used. Secondly, as a material applied to electronic PCB substrates and wind power-generation blades, SKY FLEX UGN 150, created by synthesizing epoxy resins with one-way E-glass fiber, was also used for comparative evaluation. (Table 1)

Table 1 The properties of composites

NO	Properties	Unit	Nominal mean value	
			Cycom 5276-1 G40-800-24K	UGN 150
Resin	Designation	-	Cycom 5276-1	
	Chemical type	-	Toughened epoxy resin	epoxy resin
	Cure temperature	°C	175	127
	Density	g/cm ³	1.31±0.01	1.20
Cure Cycle	Curing pressure	psi	586 kPa	310 kPa
	Heat-up/Cooling rate	°C/min	0.5~3/3	1~2
	Curing temperature	°C	175	127
	Cure time	min	120	90
	Vacuum(abs. pressure)	mbar	Full vacuum	Full vacuum

Properties	0 tension strength	MPa	3013.01	SACM A SRM-	147	-
	0 tension modulus	GPa	155.13	4	7.25	-

2.2 Experimental Apparatus

The methods of detecting composite material defects by using infrared thermography are largely divided into passive methods and active methods, and unlike passive ones, the active measure methods measure the defect size by taking a particular source of stimuli as its harmonic function, delivering it to objects and processing the response signals of objects.

In this study, a conduction-typed lock-in thermal-infrared thermography system was designed to effectively detect defects of laminated composite materials, and by embodying various different devices used in the existing optical-infrared thermography system into a single system, the portability and function could be advanced, further making it possible to measure the defect size in real time.

In this study, a defect detection basic experiment was conducted on artificial defect specimen manufactured with two kinds of materials by using nondestructive testing technique using infrared and lock-in technologies out of the active methods.

The principle of lock-in thermography is based on the idea that temperature modulation induced from outside the surface of the component propagates as a "thermal wave" inside the material. As this wave undergoes reflections at boundaries like all other waves, there will be numerous reflecting thermal waves coming from the component's rear side and all internal boundaries (e.g. glued interfaces). As a consequence, the temperature modulation at the component's exposed surface is modified by thermal waves coming out from the inside of the structure. A sensitive indicator of the responding thermal wave is the phase angle between energy deposition and local thermal response. The resulting surface temperature field is monitored during the modulated

illumination with a thermography camera that takes a sequence of infrared images. A Fourier analysis performed at each pixel of the sequence of infrared images provides information of the magnitude and phase of the local response wave. These two parameters may be used to illustrate the relevant information in a different kind of imaging. The magnitude image is affected by inhomogeneities of optical surface absorption, infrared emission and distribution of optical illumination. Nevertheless, when the evaluation is performed for each pixel of the image sequence, all these physical effects will be eliminated. Hence, the so called phase image does not show any of these disturbing effects at all. For curved aerospace structures it is often difficult to maintain a homogeneous optical illumination but with a temperature modulation in a sinusoidal way, this evaluation is particularly simple because averaging procedures reduce the about 1000 initial thermography images to only 4 which are by 90 degrees out of phase giving the phase image Φ according to $\Phi = \arctan((S_3 - S_1)/(S_4 - S_1))$ where S_1 to S_4 denote the 4 images[3]. While thermography generates images where the contrast is provided by local thermal emission, lock-in thermography means that one investigates a coded heat flow by analysing the temperature modulation that is induced by periodical heat deposition: As the thermal wave is reflected at the boundaries of subsurface features, its superposition to the original thermal wave causes a signal change that depends on the depth of the hidden boundary. One can show that the relevant parameter is thermal diffusion length m given by $\mu = \sqrt{2\alpha/\omega}$ where α denotes thermal diffusivity while ω is the angular frequency of modulation: Signal magnitude is affected by boundaries in a depth that is less than m while signal phase still responds at about twice this depth.[4-6]

The infrared thermography device is composed of a heating device of light source and an infrared thermography camera, and to minimize the heat

exchange with exterior heat source during the test, a testing apparatus was installed inside the insulation chamber as shown in Fig. 1. An light-source lamp with 1kW in output and 2m in distance was used, and the infrared camera was Silver 480m Model (NEDT: 25 mK) made by French Cedip.

Fig.1 Configurations of Optical thermography system

For a better detection sensitivity of the infrared camera, the surface of composite specimens was coated with matt black paint to satisfy the same condition as absolute black body with 1 of emissivity.

3. Experiments

3.1 CFRP Specimen with 1.4mm in Thickness

Fig.2 shows images obtained by experimenting specimen compared to the defect depth, 50 % and 87.5 %, the images in the defect depth, 12.5 % and 25 %, were found to be unclear. Besides, the frequency showing the most remarkable testing result was 200 mHz.

Fig. 2 Thermography of CFRP Specimen with 1.4 mm in Thickness (200 mHz)

3.2 GFRP Specimen with 1.4mm in Thickness

Fig. 3 shows the delamination artificial defect specimen, which was designed in the same form and size as that of CFRP specimen No. 1, except the kind of material, and the defect depth was 12.5 %, 25 %, 50 % and 87.5 %.

Fig.3 Thermography of GFRP Specimen with 1.4 mm in Thickness (50 mHz)

Besides, the frequency showing the most remarkable testing result was 50 mHz. It seems that because the coefficient thermal conductivity between CFRP and GFRP is different, the heat conduction occurs faster in CFRP than GFRP since its coefficient thermal conductivity is higher.

4. Result

As a result of the experiment, shooting the same heat energy into objects has an advantage in detecting defects located in deep areas since the lower the incidence frequency gets, the deeper the beam penetrates. However, when the heat of light source is shot into objects more than a particular time period, there was a problem occurring that entire specimen gets closer to the temperature equilibrium state, making it difficult to detect defects.

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